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%load data
Mouse_function_data = '..\Function data\14d REGN\*.txt'

%view directory
directory = dir(Mouse_function_data)

%storage for loop iterations

%zeros creates an empty vector of zeros that I can store peak torque values
%in - I set them to numel(directory) because that's the column size I
%wanted, the 1 is just for making it a 1xn column

peak_torque_vals = zeros(numel(directory),1)
ROTD_vals = zeros(numel(directory),1)
%twenty_time_vals = zeros(numel(directory),1)
%eighty_time_vals = zeros(numel(directory),1)
file_names = cell(numel(directory),1)

%Looping through files

%number of files is assigned to directory
for file_counter = 1 : numel(directory)

    folder_name = directory(file_counter).folder
    file_name = directory(file_counter).name
    full_name = fullfile(folder_name, file_name)

    %read table during each iteration
    t = readtable(full_name)
    justforce = t.FilteredForce
    peak_torque = max(justforce)

    %correction factor for peak torque
    avg_base_force = mean(justforce(1:2000))
    peak_torque1 = peak_torque-avg_base_force
    corrected_force_vector = justforce-avg_base_force
    %round_corrected_force_vector = round(corrected_force_vector)

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%aurora sampling rate, make time vector
sampling_rate = 850/8500
time_vector = [0:sampling_rate:849.99]'

%extracting time and force at indices of interest (20%-80% of torque
development)
pulling_time= time_vector(2600:2900)
pulling_force= corrected_force_vector(2600:2900)

%Make best fit line eq and pull slope - this is ROTD
best_fit = polyfit(pulling_time,pulling_force,1)
ROTD = best_fit(1)
end

%Find way to display peak torque in a table
peak_torque_vals

final_vals = table(file_names, peak_torque_vals, ROTD_vals)

%for excel export
filename = 'Raw and normalized ROTDs.xlsx'
writetable(final_vals,filename,'Sheet',1,'Range','I12')

%ROTD units are mili Newton meters/.0411ms
%24.33 conversion factor to make /1ms

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